

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACT OF GREEN FINANCE DEVELOPMENT ON ENERGY CONSUMPTION INTENSITY: EVIDENCE AND IMPLICATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

Since the reform and opening up, China's economy has gradually shifted from high-speed growth to high-quality development. However, the problems of environmental pollution and energy consumption brought about by economic development need to be solved urgently, and the issue of environmental protection has attracted great attention nationwide. In this context, the state has explicitly proposed the development of green finance through supply-side structural reform, aiming to promote a new type of environmentally friendly economy. Through the development of green finance, China seeks to achieve the 2035 ecological governance and energy conservation and environmental protection goals, laying a solid foundation for the beautiful vision of building a beautiful China. Therefore, it is of great significance to study the impact of green finance on the intensity of energy consumption in order to achieve sustainable economic development, as well as to promote the synergistic development of ecological environment and economic construction.

Keywords: energy consumption, green finance, ecology, economic construction.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of China's economy, environmental pollution and energy consumption have increasingly become the focus of widespread concern in all walks of life, especially in the context of deepening globalisation, the high intensity of energy consumption has become an important factor restricting the high-quality development of China's economy. China's resource endowment shows the characteristics of 'coal-rich, oil-poor and gas-poor', resulting in China's energy structure is mainly dependent on fossil energy, especially coal-based. According to data from the National Bureau of Statistics, in 2018, China's fossil energy consumption accounted for 85% of total energy consumption, of which coal accounted for as much as 58% of primary energy, while the proportion of oil and natural gas was only 20% and 7%. More recent data show that China's energy consumption equivalent to standard coal reached 5.24 billion tonnes in 2021, a year-on-year increase of 5.2%, and coal consumption increased by 4.6% year-on-year, accounting for about 56.0% of total energy consumption. It can be seen that coal occupies an indispensable position in China's energy consumption structure, while the excessive energy consumption intensity has become a core factor affecting the sustainable development of the economy. In order to effectively deal with the problem of high energy consumption, China has gradually taken the development of green finance and green growth as an important hand and strategic support for reducing energy consumption. 2015, China promulgated the Overall Programme for the Reform of the Ecological Civilisation System, which explicitly put forward the overall goal of 'establishing a green financial system'. 2016 released the 'Guiding Opinions on Building a Green Financial System', in which it is stated that 'green financial system' is a key element in the development of China's econ-

omy. In the 'Guiding Opinions on Building a Green Financial System' issued in 2016, the key objectives and specific measures for building a green financial system were further put forward, aiming to provide policy guidance for the standardisation of green finance. In 2017, the State Council began to carry out green financial reform pilots in a number of cities. In the 'Opinions on the Complete and Accurate Implementation of the New Development Idea and Doing a Good Job in Carbon Peak Achievement and Carbon Neutral Work' issued in 2021, the government re-emphasised the importance of actively carry out the construction of a green financial system, and provide basic guidelines for financial support for the goals of 'carbon peak' and 'carbon neutrality'. It can be said that the development of green finance has become a key link in promoting China's high-quality economic development. Therefore, this paper will study the impact of green financial development on energy consumption intensity from both theoretical and empirical aspects, and strive to provide useful experience and reference for green financial development to reduce energy consumption intensity.

In the study of green bonds, Wang Banshun (2023) combines the current situation of insufficient liquidity in China's bond market to explore whether there is a green premium for green bonds. It is found that when analysing the adverse selection problem of third-party green certification, there is a positive relationship between enterprises applying for third-party green certification and their debt ratios, and private bonds are more inclined not to apply for third-party green certification compared to public bonds. Tingting Wang (2023) studies the impact of fintech on green bonds, and the results show that fintech has a significant positive driving effect on the issuance scale of green bonds. Juan David González Ruiz (2023) conducts a study on green bonds in the Caribbean region, and points out that municipal debt ceilings, credit ratings, lower solvency capacity,

the readiness of bankable projects limited, and lack of communication between the financial sector and local governments have constrained the development of the green bond market in the region. Zhu and Wang (2020) show that the impact of green bonds issued by enterprises on share prices is weak, and there is no significant financing impact relationship between green bonds and company share prices, and the ability of green bonds to attract social investment is relatively limited.

For green credit, Lin Lefen (2024) selected six major listed enterprises and explored the impact of green credit on the green performance of enterprises and its mechanism of action. It is found that the implementation of green credit significantly promotes the green performance of enterprises in the six high energy-consuming industries, mainly through promoting the green technological innovation of enterprises, and has a more significant impact on the green performance of state-owned high-energy-consuming enterprises. Boqiang Lin and Ting Pan (2024) study the mechanism of the impact of green credit on the stock market, and find that green credit leads to an increase in the green enterprises' stock prices and yields to increase, while those of polluting firms decrease, and investor behaviour moderates this process. Wang Yanlin (2024) analysed the impact of green credit on regional carbon emissions, pointing out that green credit suppresses regional carbon emissions by promoting green innovation and optimising industrial structure. In addition, Sun Xiangdong and Wang Yingying (2023) combined econometric analysis and regional decomposition method to explore the change of energy consumption intensity in China from a regional perspective. Wang Yaxian (2021) analysed the basic situation of carbon emissions in different regions of China's thermal power industry, and studied the regional differences in energy consumption of thermal power industry in each province by using the generalised Dixie index. Haijiao Xue (2019) compiled a hybrid energy input-output table for the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region and used an input-output structural decomposition model to analyse the energy consumption of each industrial sector in the production process when meeting the final demand, which was decomposed into the five major factors of energy structure, energy intensity, value-added rate, technological level, and final demand, and compared the similarities and differences of the energy consumption and its influencing factors of the three regions, from which the explore the potential of emission reduction. Yu Xuejiao (2016) constructed an analytical model of energy consumption intensity at the national level under the provincial perspective, explored the energy consumption intensity of different regions as well as their regional differences, and made a horizontal comparison. Wang, Chuanrong, Fan, Wenchao and Li, Minata (2011) used a provincial cluster analysis model to classify different provinces in the country into three different energy-consuming regions and calculated the differences in the development of energy consumption intensity in each region under different influencing factors.

2. DEFINITION OF CONCEPTS

Green Finance

In recent years, the development of green finance has become one of the most important initiatives for financial support of environmental protection. On 31 August 2016, the People's Bank of China (PBoC) published a policy document titled *Guiding Opinions on the Construction of a Green Financial System*, which further improves the guiding policy guidelines for the green financial system.¹ The PBoC has also published a policy document titled *Guiding Opinions on the Construction of a Green Financial System*. From the micro level, green finance is an economic activity that supports environmental improvement, responds to climate change and efficient use of resources, and is a financial service provided for investment and financing operations of projects in the fields of environmental protection, energy conservation and clean energy. From the macro level, green finance is a financial activity that focuses on supporting sustainable, environmentally friendly and low-carbon projects or industries, and is a financial practice that promotes environmental protection and sustainable development. Through green financial activities, it achieves the utility of investing in clean energy, reducing carbon emissions, and improving the efficiency of resource utilisation, ensuring a balance between economic growth and environmental protection.

The financial industry plays a crucial role in the framework of sustainable development, not only in promoting environmental protection and sustainable economic and social development through financial instruments and policies, but also in promoting the sustainability of the financial system through green financial activities. The former points out that an important feature of green finance is the effective allocation of funds, that is, green finance will be allocated to high-tech and high environmental protection field, promote the transformation of the production mode of enterprises to pay attention to green environmental protection, and advocate consumers to establish the concept of green consumption. The latter points out that the green requirements of green finance promote the sustainable development of the financial industry, avoid excessive speculative behaviour, and require the financial industry to maintain a focus on long-term interests and attention.

Energy Consumption Intensity

Referring to the research results of scholars Yue Shujing (2023)[53] 'Study on the Impact of Digital Economy on Energy Intensity', Hou Jian (2020) 141 'The Impact of Green Transformation of Manufacturing Industry on Energy Intensity under the Perspective of Environmental Regulation', and Jin Bingru (2009)[55] 'The Relationship between Energy Intensity and Technological Innovation Based on Spatial Analysis', etc., all of them define energy consumption intensity as the amount of energy consumed in the unit of GDP, so it is not necessary to define energy intensity as the amount of energy consumption per unit of GDP, so it is necessary to define energy intensity as the amount of energy consumption per unit of GDP. How much energy is consumed, so this thesis continues the scholars' definition of energy consumption intensity, taking into account the relationship between energy

consumption and the degree of economic development, the calculation method of energy consumption intensity is defined as the energy consumption of the prefecture-level city in the current year divided by the GDP of the prefecture-level city in the current year. The measurement standard is often measured in terms of how much energy is consumed by the total standard tonnes of coal, and the data are standardised after obtaining the data of energy consumption intensity. In this thesis, the value of energy consumption intensity measures the relative amount of energy consumption of prefecture-level cities, which is convenient for horizontal comparison with other prefecture-level cities with different degrees of development, in which the data on energy consumption and the GDP of prefecture-level cities in the same year come from the National Bureau of Statistics.

Sustainable Development

The theory of sustainable development refers to a development model that meets current human needs without compromising the survival and development interests of future generations. Its core principles include fairness, continuity and commonality, aiming to achieve common, coordinated, fair, efficient and multi-dimensional development goals, and Huang Zhibin and Yao Can (2015) mentioned that sustainable development is a development model that focuses on long-term interests, requiring that the current generation's production and life should be based on the premise of not affecting the use of environmental resources by future generations, i.e., leaving enough ecological and environmental resources to future generations. The theory emphasises the integration and coordination of economic, ecological and social aspects, and requires that the joint sustainable development of all three aspects be taken into account in the development process. In China, the concept of sustainable development is an important element of the scientific concept of development, and one of the three strategic objectives put forward by the Chinese Academy of Sciences in 1999, which provides scientific guidance for the promotion of China's sustainable economic and social development, and the theory of sustainable development mainly includes the following aspects.

3. ANALYSIS OF CHINA'S GREEN FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT AND ENERGY CONSUMPTION STATUS QUO

China's green financial development history

China's green finance has experienced a long period of sustained development, the development of China's green finance over the years from the initial exploration to the middle of the construction of the perfect to the late rapid development of the three major stages.

2006-2014: exploration stage

2014-2016: construction stage

2016-present: development stage

The first stage is from 2006 to 2014. As early as 2006, China's financial institutions began to explore green finance, and Industrial Bank made its first attempt to co-operate with the International Finance Corporation (IFC) in 2006 and launched the first domestic energy-saving emission reduction loan, marking the beginning of China's early preliminary exploration of green finance.

The second stage is from 2014 to 2016. China entered the initial construction stage of green finance, during which the Chinese government issued the first policy document aimed at promoting the development of green finance, 'Guiding Opinions on Actively Promoting the Development of Green Finance', which clarified the overall approach of the country to vigorously promote the development of green finance.

The third stage is from 2016 to the present. In this stage, various state departments have successively issued a number of guiding policy documents on green finance, including the Guiding Opinions on Establishing a Green Financial System jointly issued by the People's Bank of China and other relevant departments, ushering in a stage of rapid development of green finance.

Looking at the trend of green finance in recent years through the lens of green credit, it can be observed that the balance of green credit has shown a steady growth. On the basis of the year-on-year growth of total green credit, the growth rate of total green credit has also continued to climb from 20% in December 2018 to 40% in December 2022 during the period. This development trend reflects the strong growth momentum of China's green credit market. Not only does the total amount of green credit show year-on-year growth, but the growth rate is also increasing, highlighting the huge development potential of China's green credit sector. From the perspective of green credit, China's green finance has shown a steady year-on-year growth trend in recent years, and continues to maintain abundant development momentum.

The figure above examines the development trend of green finance in recent years from the perspective of China's government environmental protection expenditure instead of green support. In 2020-2022, the national finance mostly focuses on public health events,

and the environmental protection financial expenditures are in a turbulent situation, but the environmental protection expenditures in 2022 will still account for 2.07% of the total expenditures, and it can be said that the environmental protection expenditures are still an important part of China's financial expenditures.

As of 2021, China's energy consumption shows a year-on-year increase in the development trend, the growth rate of total energy consumption shows a 'W'-shaped development trend of first decline and then increase. Consumption of major energy varieties, 2012-2021, China's total coal consumption, total oil consumption, total natural gas consumption, hydropower, nuclear power, wind power and other total consumption of the overall trend of rising year by year, which compared to the other three types of energy consumption, coal consumption is still China's energy structure of the

largest consumption of energy types, with the adjustment of the energy structure in recent years, petroleum, natural gas, other energy consumption, nuclear power, hydropower and other energy consumption accounted for a share of the 'W' shape. With the adjustment of the energy structure in recent years, oil, natural gas, other nuclear hydropower and other energy consumption also increased year by year, the energy structure from the past to coal-based, other energy consumption as a supplement to the energy structure gradually changed to the structure of the energy consumption of the structure of the development of the uniform.

Consumption of China's main energy varieties (10,000 tonnes of standard coal)				
vintages	Total coal consumption	Total oil consumption	Total natural gas consumption	Total consumption of hydropower, nuclear power, wind power, etc.
2012	275464.53	68363.46	19302.62	39007.39
2013	280999.36	71292.12	22096.39	42525.13
2014	279328.74	74090.24	24270.94	48116.08
2015	273849.49	78672.62	25364.40	52018.51
2016	270207.78	80626.52	27020.78	57963.93
2017	270911.52	84323.45	31397.03	61897
2018	273760	87696	36192	66352
2019	281280.6	92622.7	38999.0	74585.7
2020	282864	94122	41832	79182
2021	293440	96940		133620

This thesis explores the mechanism of the impact of green finance on improving the labour productivity of enterprises at the micro level, which is mainly reflected in the following aspects: one is that the intervention of green finance promotes the adoption of clean technology and sustainable production methods by enterprises, including the improvement of production processes and the optimization of resource use. Through the introduction of energy-efficient technologies and methods in the production process, enterprises have improved their production efficiency and reduced their reliance on traditional energy sources, thus directly reducing the intensity of energy consumption. Secondly, the support of green finance promotes the research and development and application of clean technologies. In areas such as production and transport, producers use more energy-efficient and environmentally friendly technologies, allowing enterprises to achieve the effective use of factors of production, reducing the total amount of energy required per unit of output, which directly leads to a reduction in the overall intensity of energy consumption. The impact mechanism of green finance at the micro level is the labour productivity of enterprises at the micro level, which directly promotes the improvement of enterprises in terms of cleaner technologies and resource use, thus achieving an effective reduction in the intensity of energy consumption.

4. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Strengthen the comprehensive development of regional green finance

Research shows that green finance has a significant negative impact on energy consumption intensity. China's policymaking and financial institutions should continue to promote the development of green finance and encourage investment in low-energy consumption, clean energy and sustainable projects through incentives and support policies. Specific measures include:

- Establishing a green finance policy framework: clarifying national green finance policies and providing tax breaks and credit support to incentivise financial institutions to participate in green projects.

- Improving green financial elements: Establishing green funds, green credits and green insurance to provide low-interest loans and risk compensation for sustainable energy projects.

- Innovate green financial products: Encourage financial institutions to develop diversified green financial products to meet the needs of different investors and improve the efficiency of capital resource allocation.

- Enhance information disclosure: Set up green financial information disclosure standards to improve investor confidence in green projects.

2

Optimising industrial structure

Green finance has an important impact on energy consumption intensity by promoting industrial structure adjustment. The government should provide financial incentives and subsidies to environmentally friendly enterprises through targeted interventions, strongly support environmentally friendly technologies and sustainable production, and incentivise the development of green industries to further reduce the intensity of energy consumption.

3. Focus on green total factor production

Formulate and implement green financial policies, focusing on supporting green technological innovation and clean energy production, and promoting the upgrading of the green total factor productivity of the industrial chain. Encourage international co-operation and cross-border financial flows to jointly address the challenges of global energy consumption and promote sustainable development. Promote the application of green factors in all links of the industrial chain by incentivising enterprises to implement green production standards.

4. Promote the improvement of green innovation mechanisms

Deepen the support of green finance for green innovation to reduce energy consumption intensity, which is mainly reflected in:

- Increase R&D investment: Encourage enterprises to increase investment in green technology R&D, and provide tax incentives and research funding.

- Establish an incubation system: Provide financial and technical support for green innovation enterprises to promote the commercialisation of green technologies.

- Promote co-operation between industry, academia and research: Strengthen the co-operation between academia and industry, promote the transformation of scientific research results, and improve the efficiency of green technology application.

- Intellectual property protection: Build a sound intellectual property protection mechanism to support green technology innovation.

- Incentive mechanism: Establish incentives to encourage enterprises and individuals with outstanding contributions in the field of environmental protection, and accelerate the research and development and promotion of green technologies.

5. Strengthening cooperation on green finance development in prefecture-level cities

Due to the spatial spillover effect of green finance on energy consumption, it is recommended that the government promotes cross-regional cooperation, facilitates information and resource sharing, establishes a cross-regional green industry fund to support joint green projects in multiple locations, and at the same time establishes uniform standards to boost investor confidence. This can create healthy competition and co-operation within the region, ultimately achieving a reduction in the overall intensity of energy consumption and promoting the harmonious development of the economy and ecology. Through the establishment of co-development policies, synergies in green finance can be realised and the efficiency of energy use within the region can be improved.

5. RESEARCH CONCLUSION

Against the backdrop of global climate change and sustainable development receiving widespread attention from the international community, and as social awareness of environmental protection rises, investors and financial institutions are increasingly concerned with channelling funds to low-energy-consumption, clean-energy and sustainable development projects in order to reduce the intensity of energy consumption and promote the green development of the economy. The development of green finance has provided more financial support for renewable energy and energy efficiency improvements, and has further contributed to the global change in energy consumption patterns by directing capital flows to environmentally friendly projects. Green finance has a significant negative impact on the intensity of energy consumption, which gradually decreases as the development of green finance deepens. Green finance reduces energy intensity by promoting green total factor productivity.

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